

The Human Reference Atlas

Style Guide

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01

Logo

Symbol

The landmark represents the construction of the circular diagram of the Vasculature Common Coordinate Framework (VCCF). It also denotes a red blood cell, serving as the essential unit for scale measurement across the HRA.

For scales of 48 pixels by 48 pixels and below, use the smaller size landmark variant.

Primary Logo

The HRA logo consist of two parts- the wordmark and the brandmark (symbol).

Human
Reference
Atlas

Brandmark

Wordmark

Clear Space

The HRA logo should always be surrounded by a minimum area of space. Please avoid placing other elements closer than the defined exclusion zone.

Color Usage

There are a variety of color options for each variation of the HRA logo. The red logo is the primary choice and to be used when possible. Black out or white out logos should only be used for low contrast settings.

1. Full color

2. White out

3. Black out

Human
Reference
Atlas

1. Red Text

Human
Reference
Atlas

2. White Text

Incorrect Usage

Please avoid executions which misuse the logo in order to preserve integrity. Below are examples of incorrect usage.

⊘ Do not deform, distort or crop

⊘ Do not alter the font

⊘ Do not change the distance or proportions

⊘ Do not add any effects

⊘ Do not rotate

02

Color

Primary Color Palette

Red 1 is the primary brand color. Use it judiciously to draw attention to key elements or actions, such as call-to-action buttons. Avoid Red 1 to fill large blocks of color.

HEX #FF0043

RGB 255, 0, 67

CMYK 0, 100, 74, 0

Usage Brandmark, primary CTA buttons, background fill for organ icons

HEX #201E3D

RGB 32, 30, 61

CMYK 48, 51, 0, 76

Usage Headings, icon buttons, background fill for product icons

HEX #4B4B5E

RGB 75, 75, 94

CMYK 20, 20, 0, 63

Usage Background fill for miscellaneous icons

HEX #E6EAF0

RGB 230, 234, 240

CMYK 4, 3, 0, 6

Usage Surfaces

HEX #FFFFFF

RGB 255, 255, 255

CMYK 0, 0, 0, 0

Usage Backgrounds, icon fills

UI Color Palette

These accessible colors should be used to supplement primary palette for user interface elements.

Red 2

HEX #E00D3A
RGB 224, 13, 58
CMYK 0, 83, 65, 12

Red 3

HEX #B20A2F
RGB 178, 10, 47
CMYK 0, 94, 74, 30

Gray 1

HEX #26262C
RGB 38, 38, 44
CMYK 14, 14, 0, 83

Gray 2

HEX #F8FAFC
RGB 248, 250, 252
CMYK 2, 1, 0, 1

Gray 3

HEX #FCFCFC
RGB 252, 252, 252
CMYK 0, 0, 0, 1

Blue 4

HEX #D5DBE3
RGB 213, 219, 227
CMYK 6, 4, 0, 11

Blue 5

HEX #EFF2F5
RGB 239, 242, 245
CMYK 2, 1, 0, 4

Visualization Colors: Dark Mode

Dark mode colors are designed to appear over Blue 1 background. Use Red 1 to highlight the most critical elements of a composition or key pieces of information.

Red 1	HEX #FF0043 RGB 255, 0, 67 CMYK 0, 100, 74, 0 Usage Highlighting important parts of visualizations		
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These palettes can serve as a starting point and may be adapted as needed.

HEX #8498AD RGB 132, 152, 173 CMYK 24, 12, 0, 32		
HEX #D6B6D7 RGB 214, 182, 215 CMYK 0, 15, 0, 16		
HEX #C8DFBE RGB 200, 223, 190 CMYK 10, 0, 15, 13		
HEX #AEA7C1 RGB 174, 167, 193 CMYK 10, 13, 0, 24		
HEX #637597 RGB 99, 117, 151 CMYK 34, 23, 0, 41		

Visualization Colors: Light Mode

Light mode colors are intended for use on Blue 3, Blue 5, and Gray 3 backgrounds. Again, use Red 1 for main focal areas.

Gray 3 HEX #FCFCFC RGB 252, 252, 252 CMYK 0, 0, 0, 1	Blue 3 HEX #E6EAF0 RGB 230, 234, 240 CMYK 4, 3, 0, 6	Blue 5 HEX #EFF2F5 RGB 239, 242, 245 CMYK 2, 1, 0, 4	Red 1 HEX #FF0043 RGB 255, 0, 67 CMYK 0, 100, 74, 0
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Feel free to adapt palette as needed, provided sufficient contrast is maintained.

HEX #7495AE RGB 32, 30, 61 CMYK 48, 51, 0, 76		
HEX #D6B6D7 RGB 214, 182, 215 CMYK 0, 15, 0, 16		
HEX #8DC599 RGB 141, 197, 153 CMYK 28, 0, 22, 23		
HEX #A294C9 RGB 162, 148, 201 CMYK 19, 26, 0, 21		
HEX #59678E RGB 89, 103, 142 CMYK 37, 27, 0, 44		

03

Typography

Primary Typeface

Metropolis Medium/500 is the HRA primary typeface. It is a modern and versatile sans serif font that is used for all HRA headings, labels, and buttons. *

Aa

Metropolis Medium/500

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

0123456789!@#\$%^&*()_+='<>./?*

*In the case that Metropolis is unavailable, Montserrat semi-bold may also be used (e.g. presentation decks).

Secondary Typeface

Nunito Sans Regular/400 is the secondary typeface which is only used for paragraph text

Aa

Nunito Sans Regular/400

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

0123456789!@#\$%^&*()_+='<>./?*

Mono Typeface

Roboto Mono Medium/500 is the HRA primary mono typeface. It should be exclusively used for code-related headings and labels in developer-focused applications.

Aa

Roboto Mono, Medium/500

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789!@#\$%^&*()_+=;'<>,./?*

04

Iconography

Iconography Overview

HRA icons are a key part of our design language and are used across all interfaces. HRA has custom icons for organs, app products, data products, navigation, and more.

App Product Icons

Data Product Icons

Organ Icons

Miscellaneous Icons

Optimal usage of HRA iconography includes:

- All icons are limited to a fill version to stay consistent. Do not use HRA icons with outlines or strokes.
- App and data product logos exist as a branded house and use a white fill (#FFFFFF) with a background color of HRA Blue 1 (#201E3D).
- Organ icons are to use a white fill (#FFFFFF) on HRA Red 1 (#FF0043).
- Miscellaneous icons, used visually, use a white fill (#FFFFFF) on top of HRA Blue 2 (#4B4B5E).

App Product Icons

Several tools and applications are needed to build and scale the evolving Human Reference Atlas. Each app product has it's own icon.

	Exploration User Interface apps.humanatlas.io/eui		
	HRApop Visualizer apps.humanatlas.io		
	Human Atlas Stories apps.humanatlas.io		
	Functional Tissue Unit Explorer apps.humanatlas.io/ftu-explorer		
	Knowledge Graph lod.humanatlas.io		
	Organ Gallery Meta link		
	Registration User Interface apps.humanatlas.io/rui		
	Tissue Origin Predictor apps.humanatlas.io		
	Web Components apps.humanatlas.io		

Data Product Icons

Digital objects are the foundation of the HRA Knowledge Graph. Digital objects build and interconnect the HRA. Each data structure has its own icon.

3D Reference Objects

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=ref-organ

Landmarks

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=landmark

ASCT+B Tables

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=asct-b

Millitomes

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=millitome

Cell Type Annotation Crosswalks

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=ctann

Schema

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=omap

Collections

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=collection

Vascular Geometry

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=millitome

Dataset Graphs

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=ds-graph

Vocabulary

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=millitome

Functional Tissue Unit Illustrations

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=2d-ftu

Graphs

apps.humanatlas.io/kg-explorer/?do=graph

Organ Icons

Adipose tissue

All organs

Anatomical systems

Bladder

Blood

Bone marrow

Brain

Breast

Extrapulmonary bronchus

Eye

Fallopian tube, left

Fallopian tube, right

Heart

Intervertebral disc

Kidney, left

Kidney, right

Kidneys

Knee

Large intestine

Larynx

Liver

Lung, left

Lung, right

Lungs

Lymph nodes

Manubrium

Mouth

Muscular system

Organ Icons, continued

Ovaries

Ovary, right

Ovary, left

Mouth

Pancreas

Pelvis

Placenta

Prostate

Renal pelvis,
left

Renal pelvis,
right

Skin

Small intestine

Spinal cord

Spleen

Sternum

Stomach

Thymus

Trachea

Uterer, left

Uterer, right

Uterus

Vasculature,
thick

Vasculature,
thin

Miscellaneous Icons

Miscellaneous icons used throughout the Human Reference Atlas Portal.

Biomarker

Used on count cards to display total number of biomarkers in the HRA

Cell types

Used on count cards to display total number of cell types in the HRA

Contribute

Used on count cards to display total number of consortia contributing to the HRA

Data

Used for the Data Overview page: humanatlas.io/overview-data

Documentation

Used for Help & Documentation pages

Experts

Used on count cards to display the number of experts contributing to the HRA

Explore

Used for the Apps Overview page: docs.humanatlas.io/apps

Publications

Used on count cards to display the number of publications linked to the HRA

05

Imagery

Imagery Overview

HRA imagery is vibrant, diverse, inclusive, modern and is created at the intersection of nature and technology. Imagery should use curated and nuanced color palettes (using visualization colors). However, the HRA primary and secondary palette should be used for any UI elements appearing on imagery. Large blocks of background colors for imagery can use shades of the HRA blues and grays. Avoid highly saturated colors.

3D illustrations and animations are highly organic with translucent materials and use of red hues.

2D illustrations and animations use blocked colors with no harsh outlines.

